

D6.1 - INITIAL DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION PLAN

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Abstract

The transition from linear fossil-based systems to circular and bio-based systems represents an opportunity and a suitable pathway for achieving several SDGs. Indeed, circular bio-based systems depict a great opportunity to reconcile sustainable long-term growth with environmental protection through the prudent use of renewable resources for industrial purposes. This needed transition is a complex process, which does not simply require innovative technologies from the supply-side, but also societal transformations based on a multi-actor process. The circular bioeconomy meta-sector may be a good candidate to put forward a new economic model, which requires transformative policies, purposeful innovation, access to finance, risk-taking capacity as well as new and sustainable business models and markets. However, a critical assessment of the environmental, social and economic impacts of the current linear fossil-based economy, as well as of the improvement potential associated with circular bio-based systems, is needed to underpin the identification of policy priorities. Bearing this in mind, SUSTRACK is a three-year project aimed at supporting policymakers in their efforts to develop sustainable pathways to replace fossil and carbon-intensive systems with sustainable circular and biobased systems (at the EU and regional scale), contributing to achieving the European Green Deal's objectives. This will be done by: identifying environmental, economic and social limits of a linear carbon-intensive and fossil-based economy; improving existing assessment methodologies; assessing the environmental, social and economic impacts of the EU's current linear fossil-based economy; comparing multiple transition scenarios focusing on the most carbon intensive sectors; identifying priorities according to scenarios analysed in the project and develop guidelines and policy recommendations.

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Deliverable information	
Nature of the deliverable:	R*
Dissemination Level	
PU	Public, fully open, e.g. web x
CL	Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC
CO	Confidential to SUSTRACK project and Commission Services

* R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The SUSTRACK project entails a well-tailored and multifaceted strategy for maximising the project impact, both during as well as after the duration of the grant. In fact, the overarching strategy of the project is based on the following strategic pillars:

- Solid strategies for Dissemination and Communication, designed and implemented from the very early stages of the project and updated during the project's lifetime;
- Dissemination and Communication tools and activities specifically seeking to maximise:
 - Awareness of the project and its outcomes, through a package of stakeholders-tailored activities;
 - Uptake of results, through effective Dissemination and Communication activities with policy communities, research and business;
- Impact through the integration of the impact strategy in the design of all WPs from the proposal;
- Transform the project results into actionable material to be used by the stakeholders in their practice;
- Early and active engagement of stakeholders in the co-design of the requirements, solutions and processes. This will ensure that all the perspectives are taken into consideration and the outcomes are tailored to the stakeholders' needs.

This deliverable will describe the Dissemination and Communication strategy, activities and tools that will be implemented by the SUSTRACK project throughout the entire lifetime of the project. This strategy contains a variety of information meant to guide SUSTRACK partners in conveying content and messages targeted to specific audiences while adhering to the established branding. Partners are welcome and encouraged to use this information in their Communication efforts and to involve Dissemination and Communication leaders when organising/participating in Dissemination and Communication activities.

In addition, the partner responsible for Dissemination and Communication, namely FVA, will assist and support the partners in their activities connected to this aspect. The strategy will be constantly revised and updated to follow the evolution of the project.

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List of Abbreviations	
Abbreviation/Acronym	Description
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
EC	European Commission
WP	Work Package
PLRT	Permanent Liaison Round Table
EU	European Union
OS	Open Science
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
AB	Advisory Board
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment

1 INTRODUCTION

This deliverable provides detailed information about the strategies, methodologies, channels, materials and tools used to support an effective Dissemination and Communication of the project. The strategy will be updated/revised periodically to follow the project's evolution. The rest of this deliverable is divided into 6 main sections:

- Section 2 “Dissemination and Communication strategy” presents the objectives (PURPOSE), target audience (TARGET), contents (CONTENT), timeline (TIMING) and methodologies (METHOD) of the Dissemination and Communication strategy.
- Section 3 “Stakeholder engagement strategy” presents the strategy to identify, recruit and select stakeholders, collect their information into a stakeholders’ database and the engagement activities in which stakeholders will be involved.
- Section 4 “Strategy for collaboration with projects and initiatives” presents the strategy to identify and engage parallel and relevant projects and initiatives.
- Section 5 “Dissemination and Communication channels and tools” presents the different channels and tools to be used for disseminating and communicating project activities and outcomes, including the project website, Social Media accounts, YouTube channel, newsletter and media coverage.
- Section 6 “Monitoring and report” provides the templates designed for monitoring the reports of Dissemination and Communication activities, based on the official reporting template in the European Commission Participant Portal. Moreover, the strategy for monitoring and report of stakeholder engagement is described.
- Section 7 “Partners’ channels” maps information about all partners' websites, Social Media and other relevant contacts/channels.

Finally, Section 8 provides conclusions.

2 DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION STRATEGY

The main objective of this document is to provide a strategical approach in order to reach multiple audiences with targeted information by:

- a) disseminating the results to relevant target audiences to inform and enable stakeholders to adopt and use the project results (thus maximising outcomes and impact);
- b) communicating the project and its benefits to society;
- c) paving the way for the exploitation and sustainability of the project results to benefit society, the environment and the economy.

Based on the strategy defined in this Chapter, FVA will work in strict collaboration with all the partners and the coordinator to make sure that all the valuable knowledge assets and project outputs are identified and properly disseminated and communicated to the intended target beneficiaries. In particular, FVA will ensure that the project's outputs are transformed into “Actionable Knowledge”, ready to be used by the different project's beneficiaries in their practice.

The SUSTRACK Consortium partners are highly committed and will be actively involved in the Dissemination and Communication actions implementation. Partners are expected to contribute to disseminating the project in their own countries and at the European level, contribute with their contacts and networks to increase the project's impact, provide content to be disseminated and communicated through the project's channels, participate in relevant events and publish

scientific articles to promote the project and its outcomes. The partners will also make sure that these activities are timely reported to the Work Package leaders, coordinators and ultimately the European Commission.

2.1 Methodology

This section presents the methodology that will be used to reach the aforementioned objectives. The methodology will revolve around the five dimensions reported in Table 1. The combination of these dimensions provides a detailed plan for Dissemination and Communication activities.

Table 1 - Methodology dimensions

PURPOSE		<p>WHAT FOR: Definition of the expected outcomes of the Dissemination and Communication activities and the expected impact per type of stakeholder</p>
TARGET		<p>WHO: Identification of the target audiences to be informed of and engaged in project activities</p>
CONTENT		<p>WHAT: Identification of the main project outcomes to be disseminated, communicated and exploited</p>
METHOD		<p>HOW: Identification of the tools, activities and channels, tailored to the target audiences</p>
TIMING		<p>WHEN: Definition of the timeline and consortium action plan for each activity</p>

2.2 SUSTRACK objectives of the Dissemination and Communication (PURPOSE)

The main objectives (PURPOSE) of the SUSTRACK Dissemination and Communication strategy are to:

- Raise awareness and share information about findings and project’s results;
- Transform the project’s results into actionable knowledge, “ready-to-be used” and adopted by the relevant stakeholders;
- Identify and use the right channels to efficiently communicate with the target groups and relevant stakeholders;
- Produce the necessary supporting materials and tools to ensure effective Dissemination and Communication, including printed material (e.g., flyer, poster, roll-up, etc.) and digital material (videos, infographics, etc.);
- Promote liaison with existing networks, projects and initiatives to identify synergies and opportunities for collaboration (the approach for this activity is deeply described in Chapter 4);
- Facilitate regular Communication, through press releases and newsletters, to share information about the latest news and developments of the project to the media;
- Ensure stakeholder engagement and empowerment in all project activities at European and international levels (the approach for this activity is deeply described in Chapter 3).

SUSTRACK project will design and deploy a series of tools, channels and activities to better respond to the different objectives identified above.

2.3 SUSTRACK target audiences (TARGET)

A primary and a secondary target audience have been identified to be reached throughout the project, including respectively:

- Primary targets: Policy, Business and financial ecosystem, Research and innovation community, Sustainability system community, Multipliers, Other EU funded projects and initiatives;
- Secondary targets: Civil society, Media.

An additional target audience is represented by SUSTRACK partners. Table 2 further details the specific type of stakeholders.

Table 2 - SUSTRACK Target Audiences

TARGET AUDIENCES		
Target group	Type of stakeholders	Details
Primary targets	Policy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy makers at the National and EU level • National/regional authorities • Policy advisors (including think tanks)

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Programme owners, funding authorities (EU, national, regional)
	Business and financial ecosystems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Industrial value chain actors • Industrial associations/clusters/lobbies • Industrial/technology platforms • Industrial advisors (including think tanks) • Investors
	Research and innovation community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific community • Universities • Innovation centres, Science parks, Campus, incubators and technology parks, etc
	Sustainability system community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Standardisation bodies • Regulatory authorities • Certification bodies • Scheme owners • Life cycle and scenario assessment communities
	Multipliers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expert groups and communities of practice • Platforms • Foundations • Action groups • NGOs • CSOs
	Other EU-funded projects and initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BIOTRANSFORM • Parallel projects of working group in “Standardisation, certification, labelling and monitoring” • Other relevant projects • Other relevant initiatives
Secondary targets	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Civil society/citizens • Media 	

The project aims at reaching at least:

- for Primary targets:
 - 500 participants at conferences and events;
 - 700 surveys’ respondents;
 - 500 reached indirectly through communication and dissemination activities;
- for Secondary targets:
 - at least 10,000 stakeholders directly and indirectly (through the multipliers).

2.4 SUSTRACK contents for Dissemination and Communication (CONTENT)

The SUSTRACK Dissemination and Communication contents will be transversal throughout the project, but they will vary depending on the project's target audience.

In order to effectively target **Policy** and **Business/Financial ecosystem**, Dissemination and Communication messages will be tailored with the final aim of empowering them through improved knowledge, assessment tools and comparative scenarios, methods and supporting them in the identification and prioritisation of policy measures and pathways in support of the sustainable transition.

In order to effectively target the **Research and innovation community**, the **sustainability system community**, **multipliers** and other **EU-funded projects and initiatives**, Dissemination and Communication messages will be tailored with the final aim of building their robust understanding of the systemic environmental/social/economic impacts and trade-offs of fossil-based versus bio-based systems.

In order to effectively target **civil society** and **media**, Dissemination and Communication messages will be tailored with the final aim of engaging them in the sustainability debate and building a better knowledge about advanced life cycle methods, data and information to promote sustainable choices.

Regarding **SUSTRACK partners**, Dissemination and Communication will be tailored with the final aim of aligning the work of all the WPs and supporting the partners in the identification and creation of actionable knowledge and Communication contents emerging from relevant project outcomes. Moreover, the SUSTRACK communication team (FVA) will support the partners in all their activities through tools and Communication channels.

2.5 SUSTRACK Dissemination and Communication phases (TIMING)

Depending on the phases and activities of the project, the TIMING dimension defines the overall communication contents (Table 3).

Table 3 - SUSTRACK phases and tailored communication contents

PROJECT'S PHASES AND TAILORED COMMUNICATION CONTENTS		
Project's phase	Project's activities	Communication aims
1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mapping of environmental, economic and social limits of linear, carbon-intensive and fossil-based economy (WP1; T1.1, T1.2) and current knowledge to monitor the benefits of bio-based circular economy (WP2; T2.1). Selection and definition of case studies from four critical sectors (construction, textile, chemical, plastic) (T3.1, 3.2) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Collect information from stakeholders and validate the results.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of a portfolio of policy scenarios (WP4, T4.1). 	
2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prioritization of environmental, economic and social limits of the linear, carbon-intensive and fossil-based economy will be prioritised (WP1; T1.3) and knowledge related to the monitoring and assessment of the environmental and socio-economic impacts of the sustainable transition will be developed (WP2; T2.2, T2.3). • The case studies, building on the knowledge consolidated in WP2, will be exploited to assess the environmental, social and economic impacts of the sustainable transition (WP3, T3.3). • Creation of scenarios characterised by different policy targets (T4.2). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Define policy priorities and actions across different political levels and policy domains for the sustainable transition for each case study.
3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simulation and assessment of the previously defined scenarios (WP4) • Identification of policy priorities (WP5) • Provide policy recommendations and guidelines to steer and accelerate the sustainable transition, both in the case study sectors and at a wider level (WP5) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continuous engagement of stakeholders to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ validate policy recommendations and facilitate their implementation to support the sustainable transition; ○ facilitate the adoption, replication and exploitation of SUSTRACK results; • Empower stakeholders to identify the necessary conditions for the proposed transition pathways and prioritise short-, mid- and long-term actions.

WP6 will undertake the Dissemination and Communication of all these three phases, while in parallel will continue to engage secondary targets, such as civil society and the media, with the final aim of engaging them in the sustainability debate and building a better knowledge about advanced life cycle methods, data and information to promote sustainable choices.

2.6 SUSTRACK strategic approach to reach the intended target audiences (METHOD)

The following paragraphs present how the aforementioned different dimensions, namely the intended target audiences (TARGET), the contents to be communicated (CONTENTS), the objectives of Communication (PURPOSE) and the tools, channels and activities (METHOD) jointly define the strategic approach that SUSTRACK will implement. The METHOD section is further differentiated among the Dissemination and Communication activities.

2.6.1 SUSTRACK Dissemination strategy

Dissemination activities will involve specific measures for informing and enabling stakeholders to use and take up outcomes, thus maximising the impact of the action. Dissemination contents, activities, tools and channels, will be tailored to the different target beneficiaries.

In order to meet these premises, the SUSTRACK project will promote the Open Science (OS) in a twofold fashion: (a) as a principle and driver of inclusive and open practices, and (b) as a compliance rule under [Horizon Europe Open Science](#), which aims to improve the quality, efficiency and responsiveness of research; make publications available in open access; make data as open as possible and as closed as necessary; recognise and rewards the participation of citizens and end users.

These two objectives (a, b) will be achieved by:

- a. Stakeholder engagement at the local and European levels, which will be essential for inclusive practices for social change that empower and promote transparency, accountability and trust. SUSTRACK project will foster stakeholder engagement through workshops involving policy makers, industry professionals and representatives of standardisation bodies, among others, aimed at co-creating and validating the project findings (e.g., policy recommendations).
- b. Internal rules for implementing OS across all project activities, which will involve the early and open sharing of all research. This will include all public deliverables and relevant milestones, training materials, journal articles (each academic partner will allocate a share of their budget to gold open-access publications) and conference contributions, as well as drafts, pre-prints and registered reports. Partners will implement the objectives of the [European Open Science Cloud](#) (EOSC), which provides European researchers, innovators, companies and citizens with a federated and open, multi-disciplinary environment to publish, find and reuse data, as well as tools and services for research, innovation and education. Well-defined conditions will ensure trust and safeguard the public interest. In general, the project will aim at producing open and collaborative research. It will exploit the seamless access of the EOSC and ensure the FAIR (findability, accessibility, interoperability and reusability) management and reliable reuse of research data and all other digital objects produced (e.g., methods, frameworks, dashboard, technical and scientific publications). It will fully deploy the EOSC to ensure high productivity while generating new insights and innovations and improving reproducibility and trust in science. In particular, by enabling the open collaboration of scientists, the EOSC increases alignment between scientific values and scientific practices.

The table below details the Dissemination strategy (Table 4).

Table 4 - SUSTRACK Dissemination strategy

DISSEMINATION STRATEGY TARGETING THE DIFFERENT AUDIENCES			
Target	Purpose	Contents	Method
All target audiences	<p>To promote SUSTRACK activities, results, news.</p> <p>To inform and educate various target audiences.</p>	SUSTRACK activities, results, news	<p>SUSTRACK Dissemination tools:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • Press releases • Email campaigns • Newsletters • Flyers • Presentations • Roll-ups • Posters • Multimedia (promotional video, video teasers for Social Media campaigns, promotional banners, thematic cards) <p>Live and online activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Final event • Participation to external events
<p>Primary targets:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy • Business and financial ecosystem • Research and innovation community • Sustainability system community • Multipliers • Other EU-funded projects and initiatives 	<p>To make SUSTRACK outcomes 'actionable' for all stakeholders.</p> <p>To maximise the impact, replication and exploitation.</p>	SUSTRACK activities, results, outcomes, replicable formats, lessons learnt and recommendations	<p>SUSTRACK Dissemination tools:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Same Dissemination tools as above • Publications • Factsheets • Case studies videos • Infographics <p>Live and online activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European conferences (i.e., INSPIRE, DESIGN, IMPLEMENT) • National conferences (DEPLOY) • Organization of webinars, workshops, meetings, events

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • >40 Meetings with stakeholders • >10 talks at events and conferences (live and online)
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2.6.2 SUSTRACK Communication strategy

Communication activities will involve specific measures for raising awareness and promoting the project and its results, with the aim of reaching and engaging a critical mass of stakeholders, including civil society and the media. Campaigns will be designed and implemented throughout the project’s lifetime to build traction among the target audiences. These campaigns will build upon the promotion mix that focuses on creating awareness and engaging target stakeholders in project activities. Online (e.g., Social Media and web-based campaigns) and on-site/on-line/hybrid activities (e.g., workshops, capacity building) will be implemented to keep the primary targets engaged and to raise awareness and inform the secondary targets.

The table below details the Communication strategy (Table 5).

Table 5 - SUSTRACK Communication strategy

COMMUNICATION STRATEGY TARGETING THE DIFFERENT AUDIENCES			
Target	Purpose	Contents	Method
All target audiences	<p>To inform both primary and secondary targets about SUSTRACK outcomes and impacts.</p> <p>To engage civil society in the sustainability debate and to promote sustainable choices.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SUSTRACK outcomes • Impacts of the transition on the environment, society and economy • Role of EU-funded projects in promoting the transition 	<p>SUSTRACK Communication tools:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • Social Media profiles (LinkedIn, Twitter) • Social Media campaigns
<p>Primary targets:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy • Business and financial ecosystem 	<p>To promote stakeholder engagement and animation in WP1-WP5.</p> <p>To co-create shared solutions.</p>	Engage multi-stakeholders in mutual learning, co-creation and empowerment activities	<p>SUSTRACK Communication tools:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Capacity-building packages targeting policy makers, the industrial ecosystem,

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research and innovation community • Sustainability system community • Multipliers 	<p>To empower stakeholders.</p> <p>To derive lessons learnt for replicability and exploitation.</p>		<p>the research and innovation community, and the sustainability system community</p> <p>Live and online activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European conferences (i.e., INSPIRE, DESIGN, IMPLEMENT) • National conferences (DEPLOY) • Workshops • Co-creation focus-groups • Interviews • Surveys • Co-creation workshops • Webinars • DEPLOY Policy roundtable discussions • Capacity building seminars • Final event
<p>Other EU-funded projects and initiatives</p>	<p>To build an innovation ecosystem for the sustainability transition.</p>	<p>Networking and Collaborations opportunities</p>	<p>Live and online activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cooperation and alignment activities • Thematic mobilisation and mutual learning workshops • Webinars • Co-creation workshops • Final event

3 STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT STRATEGY

Stakeholder engagement is one of the main pillars of the SUSTRACK project, since the involvement of stakeholders throughout all the project’s WPs ensures that the project outcomes are shared and validated among relevant target audiences. The main objective of the stakeholder engagement activities is to connect stakeholder feedback with the project results, considering all perspectives.

Accordingly, T6.2 “Stakeholder Engagement” aims to increase stakeholder knowledge and capacities and develop shared solutions via:

- the **identification and involvement of relevant stakeholders** (i.e., policy, business and financial ecosystem, research and innovation, sustainability system community,

multipliers, other EU-funded projects and initiatives, civil society, media, etc.) to serve project's activities;

- the **establishment of a Sustrack advisory board**, which will represent the core of the stakeholder community of contributors, multipliers and adopters;
- the **organization of 3 European conferences**, aimed at both sharing the knowledge, tools and models developed by Sustrack and co-creating stakeholder-oriented content and solutions;
- the **organization of 6 national conferences** for validation and co-creation of policy recommendations;
- **support to partners in the organisation** of task-related activities with stakeholders (e.g., co-creation) in the context of the abovementioned conferences and other stakeholder engagement activities.

Part of this task consists of developing a strong stakeholder engagement strategy and associated activities that reflect a recognition of the importance of effective stakeholder engagement in achieving project success. By prioritizing engagement with stakeholders, the Sustrack project can better understand stakeholder needs and concerns, build trust and collaboration, and ultimately deliver better outcomes for all parties involved. Investing in the development of effective activities around stakeholder engagement can help to ensure that the engagement process is streamlined, efficient, and productive, reducing the risk of misunderstandings, delays, or other issues.

3.1 Identify, recruit and select Sustrack project stakeholders

Stakeholder recruitment will be an iterative, ongoing and dynamic process rather than a one-time event. It will be viewed as a continuous process that requires input and participation from all project partners. This approach recognizes that stakeholders may change over time or have evolving needs and expectations, and therefore, requires ongoing effort and adaptation to ensure that all parties are engaged and informed. By embracing stakeholder recruitment as an iterative and living process, the Sustrack project can foster more effective collaboration, build stronger relationships with stakeholders, and ultimately improve project outcomes.

Sustrack adopts a multi-stakeholder approach. Stakeholders' categories and subcategories have been identified in Table 2, but their involvement will vary depending on the objectives and expected outcomes for each of the Sustrack activities with them. A detailed overview of activities, expected results, target participants, KPI and timing is provided in Section 3.3.2.

By providing a structured approach to stakeholder recruitment, the stakeholder engagement strategy can help to ensure that stakeholders are identified and engaged in a systematic and targeted way. The four identified sectors that face critical challenges within the current linear system provide a framework for understanding stakeholder needs and expectations and can help project teams to tailor their engagement efforts accordingly.

3.1.1 Sustrack stakeholders' database

To ensure the participation of the most relevant stakeholders for the Sustrack project, the partners, under the leadership of PC and FVA, will setup and continuously develop an extensive database of stakeholders, which will serve as a base to select the most appropriate stakeholders to be involved in various engagement activities.

To that aim the Database has the following structure:

- Type of stakeholder
 - Policy
 - Business and financial ecosystem
 - Research and innovation community
 - Sustainability system community
 - Multipliers
 - Other EU funded projects and initiatives
 - Civil society/citizens
 - Media
 - Other

Stakeholder details:

- Stakeholder name (organisation)
- Brief description
- Country
- Link
- Sector of interest
 - Plastic
 - Construction
 - Textile
 - Chemical
 - Other (please specify)
- Relevant Social Media contacts of the stakeholder

Furthermore, two additional sections are also provided to facilitate reaching the stakeholder:

- SUSTRACK Partner suggesting the stakeholder
- If the Partner has direct access to stakeholder contacts

NOTE: It was decided, both for GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation) and for the partner's IPR protection, to populate the shared database inserting only the stakeholder's type and company data and the domain of interest. The sensitive data are stored in each partner's database and will be activated based on the project's needs, by the responsible partners.

The SUSTRACK Stakeholder's Database belongs to the project and it is not publicly available. It will be a crucial tool for the project's partners in selecting stakeholders for the project events. Its creation and maintenance will be an ongoing activity, with the database continuously updated with new entries and the removal of outdated ones. PC is responsible to oversee the activities regarding the database and will check that the information is up to date. This database will help ensure that project events are attended by relevant stakeholders, enabling effective communication and engagement with key individuals and organizations.

3.1.2 SUSTRACK online form for spontaneous expression of interest

In order to streamline the recruitment process and facilitate the engagement of stakeholders out of partners' networks by facilitating the collection of spontaneous expressions of interest, an online form has been developed to support stakeholder recruitment and it is available on the [SUSTRACK website](#).

The structure of the online form is the following:

- Name
- Email address
- Institution
- Country
- In which of the four sectors are you interested in?
 - Construction
 - Textile
 - Chemical
 - Plastic
- I wish to engage with SUSTRACK project as:
 - Policy
 - Business and financial ecosystem
 - Research and innovation community
 - Sustainability system community
 - Multipliers
 - Other EU funded projects and initiatives
 - Civil society/citizens
 - Media
 - Other
- Tell us more about your role and your interest in being part of SUSTRACK stakeholders' community

3.1.3 Stakeholder recruitment strategy

In order to broaden the pool of stakeholders in the SUSTRACK project, a variety of recruitment strategies will be employed:

- **Direct invitation** of stakeholders identified during the **case study analyses**;
- **Direct invitation** of relevant stakeholders identified through **partners' suggestions** and **desk research**, mapping related documents, initiatives, associations, projects and other relevant sources;
- **Engage the responders of surveys** planned in tasks T1.2.2 and T5.1;
- **Reach out and inform stakeholders who showed their interest** (e.g., through the online form or during events, workshops and conferences, etc.) in the topics addressed by the SUSTRACK project;
- Alignment, planning and promotion of stakeholder engagement activities in **collaboration with other parallel projects** (see Chapter 4) and **relevant initiatives** (such as [ECOSYSTEMX](#), see Chapter 4);
- **Campaigns** tailored to each of the four identified sectors (e.g., with extraction from case studies analyses to tease specific sectorial stakeholders and invite them) launched both on **SUSTRACK Social Media** (Twitter and LinkedIn) and via **e-mail**;
- **Leveraging the networks and channels of project partners**, including the [European Bioeconomy Network](#) (EuBioNet, *a proactive alliance of more than 140 EU-funded projects and initiatives dealing with Bioeconomy promotion, communication and support*), by launching specific **calls for interest** to attract potential stakeholders who may have an interest in taking part of SUSTRACK activities;
- Wide distribution via partners' networks and channels of **periodic press releases and newsletters** aimed to recruit and keep stakeholders informed and engaged with SUSTRACK activities.

3.2 SUSTRACK advisory board

The establishment of a SUSTRACK Advisory Board (AB) will represent the core of the stakeholder community of contributors, multipliers and adopters. The AB will offer strategic guidance on crucial project stages and aid in engaging other stakeholder communities. PC has taken the initiative to draft a comprehensive plan and guide for partners, detailing the necessary steps to follow for the selection process. Along with the guide, PC also shared essential documents (such as Terms of Reference, available on the SUSTRACK internal consortium repository) with the partners to ensure a smooth procedure. As of now, the selection of AB members is underway, indicating that the potential candidates are being approached.

3.2.1 Advisory Board Role

The core mission of the SUSTRACK Advisory Board (AB) is to represent the stakeholder community of contributors, multipliers, and adopters. The AB will act as a consultation and validation body for the SUSTRACK project, providing strategic guidance on key stages of the project and expertise on an *ad-hoc* basis. The AB will offer valuable feedback to the project's consortium aimed at improving the SUSTRACK outcomes and engagement of the project's stakeholders.

The SUSTRACK AB members will provide their expertise on the needs and challenges that the SUSTRACK stakeholder groups are currently facing as well as contribute actively to the project's co-creation events.

The members of the SUSTRACK AB shall help access important stakeholder communities across Europe and drive the widespread acceptance and upscale of the SUSTRACK project results by informing and inviting their contacts and networks to benefit from them.

More specifically, SUSTRACK AB is accountable for:

- Fostering collaboration;
- Facilitating access and extending the reach of our consortium to important European stakeholder communities;
- Supporting the wide-spread acceptance and replication of our activities, by acting as project ambassadors who will inform and invite their networks to benefit from them when they are available.

To fulfil this role, SUSTRACK AB will be committed to:

- Represent the core of the stakeholder community of contributors, multipliers and adopters;
- Facilitate the engagement of additional stakeholder communities;
- Engage with other relevant EU-funded projects, facilitating mutual learning opportunities, dialogue, knowledge, and the exchange of best practices;
- Participate actively in INSPIRE, DESIGN, and IMPLEMENT conferences and co-creation activities to ensure high-quality output;
- Interact on an *ad-hoc* basis, if deemed necessary.

3.2.2 Benefits for Advisory Board members

As part of the strategy for attracting AB members, the SUSTRACK project offers several benefits, which have been highlighted in the Term of Reference, namely:

- Networking opportunities and visibility as an expert stakeholder in a large multi-stakeholder community;
- A dedicated section on the SUSTRACK website with the profiles of the AB members including a photo and short professional resume (optional, in agreement with each AB member);
- First and personalized access to meaningful insights generated within the context of the project and its activities;
- Unique opportunity to align the outcomes of SUSTRACK with the needs of their networks.

3.2.3 Terms of Membership

As The SUSTRACK AB will be composed of 5-10 members and will be comprised of eminent personalities from diverse backgrounds including, but not limited to, the following fields and sectors.

Fields:

- bioeconomy;
- sustainable transition;
- innovation;
- policy-making;
- governance;

Sectors:

- business community
- academia
- civil society
- regional/ national/ international public authorities.

Although individual members of the AB may be selected because of their affiliations with key organisations, they serve on the AB in their individual capacity to represent the interests and views of their stakeholder communities. Equally, members of the AB may not delegate another person to carry out the role expected from them or be replaced by any other person without prior written agreement.

Members of the AB are appointed for the duration of the project (36 months, from 1st November 2022 to 31st October 2025). If due to job changes or attrition, the AB loses links to important networks or constituencies, the consortium may decide to fill in this gap and appoint additional members.

The contribution of AB members is on a *pro bono* basis. In case a physical presence will be required from any Advisory Board member, this will first be decided by the Project Management Committee (PMC). In such a case, travel and subsistence expenses will be reimbursed by the project.

Although active engagement is expected, participation in the AB activities is entirely voluntary. There will be no adverse consequences if an AB member decides not to participate or withdraw at any stage. In fact, AB members may withdraw their participation at any time by informing the SUSTRACK Project Coordinator, UnitelmaSapienza University of Rome (UNIT) or the Advisory Board Manager, PEDAL CONSULTING (PC). They may as well request for their data to be withdrawn without giving a reason and without prejudice. Anonymous data already collected will be used

because we cannot trace the information back to a specific person, but no further data or input will be collected, or any other procedure will be carried out in relation to the specific member.

Experts who agree to join the AB will be requested to sign the SUSTRACK AB Declaration of Acceptance (DoA), according to which they will commit to:

- Abide by the SUSTRACK AB Terms of Reference (as presented herein);
- Participate in the AB in their individual capacity and not delegate another person to carry out any expected work without the prior written agreement;
- Participate in the AB with complete independence and without conflict of interest;
- Agree not to divulge any information given in the context of the work of the AB and to respect the confidentiality requirements;
- Provide input or contribution as members of the SUSTRACK AB which may be used by SUSTRACK for reporting purposes and/or to support co-creation activities of SUSTRACK.

3.3 Stakeholder engagement activities

Stakeholder engagement activities are transversal to all WPs. Based on what the WP needs to do, the partner responsible for stakeholder engagement (PC) will support WP and task leaders in defining how stakeholders will be engaged in the specific activities and what will be the expected outcomes of their contribution. Moreover, PC will provide support to partners in organizing task-related activities with stakeholders, such as co-creation.

To support these activities, PC and FVA prepared an online tool ([MIRO Board](#)) to facilitate the visualization and manage project events timely, get detailed information on the activities (e.g., target audience, EU/National level, Online/offline etc.) and identify synergies between the events, to better streamline project activities.

3.3.1 The SUSTRACK milestone conferences

In the key moments of the project, SUSTRACK will organise milestone conferences, in order to:

- stimulate debate over the sustainable transition;
- keep stakeholders engaged with SUSTRACK activities;
- increase and consolidate stakeholder knowledge and capacities and co-create shared solutions;
- enable stakeholder contributions to and validation of SUSTRACK activities;
- create actionable knowledge and facilitate the adoption and exploitation of project outcomes.

Table 6 summarizes the timeline, activities planned, expected results, participants and KPIs per each conference:

- 3 European conferences (INSPIRE, DESIGN, IMPLEMENT), aimed at both sharing the knowledge, tools and models developed by the SUSTRACK project and co-creating stakeholder-oriented content and solutions;
- 6 National conferences (DEPLOY) in Italy, Spain, Germany, Slovakia, Netherlands, and Belgium, in order to fine-tune the SUSTRACK approach through localised validation activities and co-create policy recommendations (both sector- and country-specific). The local DEPLOY conferences will also empower stakeholders through capacity-building activities;

- A Final event in order to present the SUSTRACK outcomes to the EC and other relevant stakeholders.

Table 6 - SUSTRACK conferences and related activities

OVERVIEW OF SUSTRACK MILESTONE CONFERENCES					
Conference name and responsible	Month	Activities	Expected results	Target participants	KPI
INSPIRE (Resp: PC+FVA)	M12	Conference - T6.2	To share the knowledge, tools and models developed by SUSTRACK project (T1.1, T1.2, T2.1, T5.1) and co-create stakeholder-oriented contents and solutions	EU level: Primary targets	> 100 (EU level)
		Co-creation workshop (resp. UNIT+TECNALIA) - WP3 - MS10	To discuss the case studies	4 sectors stakeholders working groups	At least 10 stakeholders per each sector (total 40)
		Scenario workshop T4.1	To verify scenarios developed in T4.1 and contribute to T5.1	4 sectors stakeholders working groups	At least 10 stakeholders per each sector (total 40)
DESIGN (Resp: PC+FVA)	M20	Conference - T6.2	To share the knowledge, tools and models developed by SUSTRACK project and co-create stakeholder-oriented contents and solutions	EU level: Primary targets	> 50 (EU level)

		Co-creation workshop (resp BAM+KE) - WP3 - MS10	To discuss the case studies to define policy priorities and actions across different political levels and policy domains for the sustainable transition, in light of the results of WP3 and WP4; improving the tools and methods of WP2 and WP4	4 sectors stakeholders working groups	At least 10 stakeholders per each sector (total 40)
IMPLEMENT (Resp: PC+FVA)	M28	Conference - T6.2	To share the knowledge, tools and models developed by SUSTRACK project and co-create stakeholder-oriented contents and solutions and facilitate the adoption, replication and exploitation of SUSTRACK results	EU level: All target audiences	> 100 (EU level)
		Co-creation workshop (resp DBFZ+CIRCE) - T5.3, MS10	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To identify the necessary conditions for the proposed transition pathways; To prioritise short-, mid- and long-term actions; To validate policy recommendations (T5.3) 	4 sectors stakeholders working groups	At least 10 stakeholders per each sector (total 40)

DEPLOY (Resp: country partners: Italy-UNIT/FVA; Spain-TECNALIA/CIRCE; Germany-BAM/DBFZ; Slovakia-PC; Netherlands-WR; Belgium-UGENT)	M30>M34	Conference - T6.2	To share the knowledge, tools and models developed by SUSTRACK project and co-create stakeholder-oriented contents and solutions	National level: All target audiences	30 participants in each of 6 countries (180 in total)
		6 Policy roundtable discussions in the partners' respective countries (country partners) - T5.3, MS11	To present the revised policy recommendations and guidelines, and ensure that the recommendations and guidelines (both sector- and country specific) are taken up in future policy development	Selected regional and national policy makers	30 participants in each of 6 countries (180 in total)
		Capacity building for local stakeholders in the context of the DEPLOY conference - T4.3, T5.2	To empower local stakeholders through at least one capacity building seminar, to analyse the implementation of the potential transition paths, based on their contextual specificities (e.g., geographical, social, cultural)	Primary targets	At least 10 stakeholders per each country (6 countries, total 60 participants)
Final Event (Resp: FVA)	M36	Final event - MS12	To present the SUSTRACK outcomes	EC and All target audiences	At least 50 participants

3.3.2 Overall details of SUSTRACK stakeholder engagement activities

Table 7 provides an overview of SUSTRACK stakeholder engagement activities, expected results, target audiences, KPIs and timeline.

Table 7 - Overview of SUSTRACK stakeholder engagement activities

STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT ACTIVITIES				
Activities	Expected results	Target participants	KPI	Month
Co-creation focus group (T1.2.1)	To validate the limits of a linear carbon-intensive and fossil-based economy identified in T1.1	Quadruple Helix (policymakers, businesses, Research and innovation community, NGOs, citizens, etc.)	15 stakeholders	M8
T1.2.2: Interviews in English and partner's languages	To complement focus group results	Quadruple Helix (policymakers, businesses, Research and innovation community, NGOs, citizens, etc.)	20 interviews with experts (from at least 10 Member States)	M8>M13
T1.2.2: Survey	To complement focus group results. The results will be shared during the INSPIRE conference (M12).	European and national policy makers, industry professionals, Research and innovation community, NGOs and citizens	Sent to 400 stakeholders in at least 10 Member States, target at least 50 answers (D1.2, M15)	M11
T1.3: Online workshops/meetings	To prioritise identified limits, to produce preliminary guidelines and policy recommendations	European and national policy makers, industry professionals, Research and innovation community, NGOs and citizens	At least 15 participants across the EU (D1.2, M18)	M13>M15
WP2-WP5: Co-creation workshops per each of the 4 working groups	To co-create case studies of relevance for the circular bio-economy	4 sectors stakeholders working groups (a) the construction sector; (b) the textile sector; (c) the (fine) chemical	3 co-creation workshops per each of the 4 working groups (> 250 participants across 12	M1>36

		sector; and (d) the plastic sector	workshops) in the context of the INSPIRE, DESIGN, IMPLEMENT conferences	
T3.4: Thematic webinars	To transfer knowledge (conclusions and recommendations for the four biobased sectors)	4 sectors stakeholders working groups	4 thematic webinars (> 100 participants, 200 views; D3.4, M30)	M23>30
T4.1: A scenarios workshop in the context of the INSPIRE conference	To verify scenarios developed in T4.1	4 sectors stakeholders working groups	At least 10 stakeholders per each sector (tot 40; D4.1, M14)	M12
T4.2: Capacity building activities (materials, model tutorials and online webinars)	To transfer knowledge and support further applications of the model	Policy makers and authorities, Policy advisors, NGOs/CSOs, Industrial advisors, Industrial associations/clusters, Research and innovation community	At least 4 online webinars (1 for each sector) involving at least 20 stakeholders each, tot 80; D4.3, M32)	M20>M23
T5.1: Policy co-creation workshop, with 4 sectors stakeholders workgroups in the context of the INSPIRE, DESIGN, IMPLEMENT and DEPLOY conferences through plenary and parallel sessions	To validate derived policy priorities and examples of good policies involving the stakeholders involved in the 4 sectors and the case studies	4 sectors stakeholders working groups	At least 10 stakeholders per each sector (total 40) (D5.3, M32)	M10>M28, M30>M34

T5.1: Prioritisation survey	To provide additional validation to policy priorities and examples of good policies	NGOs/CSOs, Industrial advisors, Industrial associations/clusters, Research and innovation community	Sent to at least 300 stakeholders from at least 10 Member States, target at least 30 answers. (D5.1, D5.2, M18, M34)	M33>M34
T5.2: Capacity building for local stakeholders in the context of the DEPLOY conference	To empower local stakeholders through at least one capacity building seminar, to analyse the implementation of the potential transition paths, based on their contextual specificities (e.g., geographical, social, cultural).	Policy makers, industry professionals, sustainability, Research and innovation community, system community at national and regional levels in the 6 partner's countries	At least 10 stakeholders per each country (6 countries, total 60 participants; D5.3, D5.4, M32, M33)	M30>M34
T5.3: 6 policy roundtable	To have discussions in the partners' respective countries (country partners)	Policy makers, industry professionals, Research and innovation community, sustainability system community at national and regional levels in the 6 partner's countries	At least 30 participants in each of 6 countries (180 in total; D5.5, M36)	M30>M34
T6.2: 3 European conferences (i.e., INSPIRE, DESIGN, IMPLEMENT)*	To share the knowledge, tools and models developed by SUSTRACK project and co-create stakeholder-oriented contents and solutions	Policy makers, industry professionals, Research and innovation community, sustainability system	At least 250 participants	M1>36

		community; D6.1, D6.2, D6.3		
T6.2: 6 national conferences (i.e., DEPLOY)*	To share the knowledge, tools and models developed by the SUSTRACK project and co-create stakeholder-oriented contents and solutions	Policy makers, industry professionals, Research and innovation community, sustainability system community; D6.1, D6.2, D6.3	At least 180 participants	M1>36

*The last two lines are explained in detail in Table 6.

4 STRATEGY FOR COLLABORATION WITH PROJECTS AND INITIATIVES

SUSTRACK will promote collaborations with relevant EU-funded projects and other initiatives, building on the extensive experience and involvement of partners in several EU-funded projects in the bioeconomy and bio-based domain. For this reason, all partners have access to a number of contacts for projects and initiatives.

FVA will also facilitate connection and collaboration with the [European Bioeconomy Network](#) (EuBioNet), being the main promoter of this initiative. EuBioNet is a proactive alliance of more than 140 EU-funded projects and initiatives dealing with Bioeconomy promotion, communication and support. The main goal is to maximise the efforts, increasing the knowledge sharing, networking, mutual learning, and coordination of joint activities and events.

The main objective of this SUSTRACK activity is to cooperate with all the parallel projects dealing with standardisation, certification, labelling and monitoring. Nevertheless, SUSTRACK will encourage the collaboration with the wider community of the bioeconomy innovation ecosystem, and specifically collaboration with EU-funded projects in this domain.

4.1 Identification and engagement of relevant projects

SUSTRACK mapped the concluded and ongoing projects and initiated the collaboration from the beginning of the project. This mapping activity will proceed during the project's lifetime, ensuring that the new EU-funded projects will be timely reached and involved.

The collaboration with parallel projects takes place in three different levels of engagement (Figure 1):

- Close collaboration with BIOTRANSFORM (the sister project under HORIZON-CL6-2022-CIRCBIO-01-03);
- Knowledge exchange and alignment with parallel projects (concluded or ongoing) in standardisation, certification, labelling and monitoring;

- Other types of collaboration or consultation relevant to SUSTRACK activities, based on the specific needs identified in the Work Packages.

Figure 1 - 3 different levels of parallel projects' engagement

4.1.1 Clustering activities with BIOTRANSFORM

The main objective of this activity is to liaise with all selected projects under the topic HORIZON-CL6-2022-CIRCBIO-01-03, namely BIOTRANSFORM, on the implementation of both projects' action plans, in order to increase their impact in addressing EU long term objectives.

This objective will be implemented through the following activities (Table 8).

Table 8 - Clustering activities with BIOTRANSFORM

CLUSTERING ACTIVITIES WITH BIOTRANSFORM				
Activities	Expected results	Target participants	KPI	Month
Online "cooperation launching event"	Kick-off the collaboration to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • set up a roadmap for cooperation; • facilitate the coordination of methodologies; • ensure wide Dissemination of projects' results and the effective exchange of policy implications; • maximise projects' impact across Europe; • develop joint events and/or publications 	EC representatives and key partners from all projects	>6 participants	Before M6

Establish a Permanent Liaison Round Table (PLRT)	Creation of a Permanent Liaison Round Table to ensure proactive collaboration between the two projects	Projects' representatives	At least 2 representatives per project	Before M6
Periodic meetings	Organize at least 1 meeting every 6 months or more based on the needs identified throughout the projects to align the two projects' activities	Representatives of PLRT and WP leaders	At least 4 meetings	M6-M36

When this deliverable was finalized, the “Cooperation Launching Event” already took place online (9 March 2023). The outcomes of this workshop were useful to fine-tune the collaboration strategy. The Cooperation Launching event was considered by both projects as a great opportunity to kick-off the collaboration. The meeting involved project coordinators, communication managers and some WP leaders.

The Cooperation Launching Event, facilitated by MIRO Board interactive tool and a solid preparatory activity, led to a fruitful discussion among the project's representatives, who agreed on a joint action plan. Specifically, the projects agreed to organize thematic discussions based on the project work plan, common topics of interest and specific activities targeting similar stakeholders. Among these topics, the following have been identified as relevant:

- limits/gaps/barriers of the linear economy;
- methodologies and tools to assess sustainability;
- stakeholder engagement activities;
- reciprocal harmonization and consolidation of policy recommendations.

Moreover, SUSTRACK and BIOTRANSFORM agreed to communicate timely and mutually the relevant events and invite each other to participate in these events with the aim of inspiring and cross-fertilizing each other. Finally, the Permanent Liaison Round Table was established.

4.1.2 Clustering activities with other parallel projects and initiatives in “standardisation, certification, labelling and monitoring”

To maximise the impact of project outcomes by promoting mutual learning and the sharing of common challenges, and boosting the valorisation of existing knowledge, the project will promote the collaboration with at least 6 parallel projects in standardisation, certification, labelling and monitoring. This collaboration takes place in two different forms:

- with concluded projects, the SUSTRACK project will facilitate the knowledge transfer of exploitable assets to maximize the usage of the outcomes stemming from these projects;
- with ongoing parallel projects, the SUSTRACK project will promote mutual learning, sharing of common challenges, and the valorisation of existing knowledge within parallel projects and initiatives fostering the transition from fossil-based, carbon-intensive systems to circular, bio-based systems.

The following projects have been identified as relevant for collaboration (Table 9).

Table 9 - Projects identified for collaboration

PROJECTS IDENTIFIED FOR COLLABORATION			
Projects	Funding	Start date	End date
STAR-ProBio	BB-01-2016	01/05/2017	30/04/2020
STAR4BBI	BBI 2015	01/09/2016	31/08/2019
BIOMONITOR	BB-02-2017	01/06/2018	20/11/2022
SUSTRACK	CIRCBIO-01-03	01/11/2022	31/10/2025
BIOTRANSFORM	CIRCBIO-01-03	01/10/2022	31/03/2025
STAR4BBS	ZEROPOLLUTION-01-07	01/09/2022	31/08/2025
SUSTCERT4BIOBASED	ZEROPOLLUTION-01-07	01/06/2022	31/05/2025
HARMONITOR	ZEROPOLLUTION-01-07	01/06/2022	31/05/2025
CALIMERO	ZEROPOLLUTION-01-06	01/07/2022	30/06/2025
ALIGNED	ZEROPOLLUTION-01-06	01/10/2022	30/09/2025
BIORECER	ZEROPOLLUTION-01-05	01/09/2022	31/08/2025
3-CO	2022-GOV-01-04	01/02/2023	31/01/2026

These objectives will be implemented through the following activities (Table 10).

Table 10 - Clustering with projects in "Standardisation, certification, labelling and monitoring"

CLUSTERING ACTIVITIES WITH OTHER PARALLEL PROJECTS AND INITIATIVES IN "STANDARDISATION, CERTIFICATION, LABELLING AND MONITORING"				
Activities	Expected results	Target participants	KPI	Month
Clustering activities with other projects and initiatives	To maximise the impact of project outcomes by promoting mutual learning and the sharing of common challenges, and boosting the valorisation of existing knowledge	Other relevant projects and initiatives	Collaborations with at least 6 projects and initiatives	M1>M36
Thematic mobilisation and mutual learning (MML) workshop	In the first MML, projects will share methodologies, lessons learnt and findings.	Other relevant projects and initiatives	At least 30 participants in total	M3
Thematic mobilisation and mutual learning (MML) workshops	In the second MML, projects will provide insights to refine the SUSTRACK results and recommendations, and will facilitate the exploitation of the project outcomes.	Other relevant projects and initiatives	At least 30 participants in total	M30

In preparation for the SUSTRACK kick-off, in the context of the workshop "Projects2Projects" organized by EuBioNet as a satellite event of the "High-Level Bioeconomy Conference" (6-7 October 2022, Brussels), some SUSTRACK partners supported the EuBioNet in facilitating the discussion among projects involved in "Standardisation, certification, labelling and monitoring". The main outcome of this workshop was the establishment of a thematic working group on these topics, to pave the way to further activities under the SUSTRACK project.

On 14 February 2023, SUSTRACK organized online the first Mobilization and Mutual Learning (MML) Workshop of the working group in "Standardisation, certification, labelling and monitoring", in collaboration with EuBioNet. All the 12 projects invited participated in the workshop, with a total of 40 participants. This workshop has been an important stepping stone for future collaborations among projects with similar focus and facilitated the uptake of exploitable assets stemming from concluded projects by the recently started projects under Horizon Europe. Many opportunities for collaboration have been identified and will serve as guidance for defining collaboration strategies among projects, namely:

- establish advisory boards with representatives of all projects;
- promote collaboration among communication managers;
- align stakeholder engagement activities;
- encourage continuous mutual learning among projects;
- jointly identify exploitation pathways.

In addition, projects agreed on discussing further common challenges and activities, such as:

- identification of criteria for value chains prioritization;
- monitoring frameworks at EU/country/region/city/value-chain/product levels.

Moreover, all projects participating at the MML agreed to become SUSTRACK “Sister Projects”, in order to leverage each other’s website for visibility exchange. The SUSTRACK website has a dedicated [“Sister Projects” section](#), where other projects are briefly presented and linked (see Section 5.2.2). Thus, Sister Projects are included in this section, and SUSTRACK is (or will be) included in theirs.

4.1.3 Clustering activities with other projects and initiatives in bioeconomy

In parallel with the abovementioned focused collaborations and activities, SUSTRACK will encourage collaboration with the wider community of the bioeconomy innovation ecosystem, and specifically the collaboration with EU-funded projects in this domain. This collaboration will be mainly facilitated by EuBioNet, in which [SUSTRACK is partner](#) since the beginning of the project.

Furthermore, the collaboration with relevant initiatives like the [“European Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform”](#), will be promoted by this task. As an example, SUSTRACK joined the [ECOSYSTEMEX initiative](#), involving 17 EU-funded projects focusing on textile sustainability and circularity (Figure 2).

Figure 2 - The ECOSYSTEMEX initiative

5 DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION CHANNELS AND TOOLS

5.1 Contents creation

The content creation phase will consist of the identification and transformation of SUSTRACK outputs (e.g. deliverables, materials, recommendations, etc.) into concise, attractive, user-friendly visual materials. The materials will include a summary of the contents, accompanied by graphical elements (e.g., infographics, images, etc.) to guide readers to a deeper understanding of the project outcomes. They will also encourage readers to visit the project website, download documents and get in touch with the SUSTRACK Consortium, thus contributing to the overall project impact.

5.2 Overview of Dissemination and Communication channels and tools

Table 11 lists all the channels and tools envisaged for the project with the KPIs to be achieved and the delivery month. This table is a live document and will be updated as the project evolves.

Table 11 - SUSTRACK Dissemination and Communication channels and tools

OVERVIEW OF DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION CHANNELS AND TOOLS			
Category	Channel/Tool	KPIs	Target Audience
Brand identity	Brand identity kit (Logo, Templates, Guidelines)	#1 (M1)	All target audiences
SUSTRACK Website	Website	#1 (M3) with >10,000 visits from >25 countries	All target audiences
Promotional material	Flyers	#2, 500 distributed (M6-M24)	All target audiences, but mainly primary targets
	Roll-ups	#2 (M6, M24)	All target audiences, but mainly primary targets
	Posters	>2 (M6, M24)	All target audiences, but mainly primary targets

	Presentations about the project and its achievements	On demand	All target audiences
Publications and actionable knowledge	Publications	>6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy • Business and financial ecosystem • Research and innovation community • Sustainability system community
	Case study factsheets (one per each sector)	At least #4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy • Business and financial ecosystem • Research and innovation community • Sustainability system community
	Conference outcome factsheets	#3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy • Business and financial ecosystem • Research and innovation community • Sustainability system community
	Case studies videos (one per each sector)	At least #4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy • Business and financial ecosystem • Research and innovation community • Sustainability system community
	Infographic cards (providing technical information/data on general questions connected to LCA, monitoring the transition, impacts...)	#20	All target audiences, but mainly primary targets
	Toolkits to make the actionable knowledge easily accessible to the stakeholders in	#6 (1 per country) + #1 in English	Mainly primary targets in the 6 target countries

	the 6 target countries (IT, NL, SK, DE, BE, ES)		
Multimedia	Promotional video	#1 (M8)	All target audiences
	Video teasers for Social Media campaigns	#2	All target audiences
	Promotional banners	>10	All target audiences
	Thematic cards (more general contents aimed at inform and educate all target audiences - general and connected to the four specific sectors)	#10	All target audiences
Dissemination and communication materials	Email campaigns	#10	All target audiences
	Newsletters	>3 (M12, M24, M36)	All target audiences
	Press releases	>4 (M1, M12, M24, M36)	All target audiences
Social Media	Social Media profiles (LinkedIn, Twitter)	#2 (M3), >3000 followers, >1000 posts	All target audiences
	Additional: YouTube		
	Social Media campaigns	>4	All target audiences

5.2.1 Brand identity

A recognisable visual identity was designed and produced at the early stage of the project's course. The **SUSTRACK logo** was designed following the idea of **transition from linear to circular** and the **4 carbon-intensive sectors the project will target**. The figure below describes the main key design concepts (Figure 3).

Figure 3 - Design concepts

In the figures below the alternatives of the logo on a dark background/on a grey scale (Figure 4) are examples of the SUSTRACK logo on cards, gadgets and clothing (Figure 5) and are reported.

Figure 4 - Logo's alternatives

Figure 5 - Example of the SUSTRACK logo on cards, gadgets and clothing

Sober fonts and colour palettes have been used considering the main target audience of the project, namely policy makers (Table 12). The colours also recall the transition from fossil (grey) to circular biobased (soil for brown and variations from brown to green).

Logo font type: **Square 721 Extended BT**

Table 12 - Logo colour palette

COLOURS						
CMYK	C: 45	C: 20	C: 18	C: 18	C: 17	C: 52
	M: 0	M: 10	M: 25	M: 21	M: 13	M: 51
	Y: 95	Y: 60	Y: 53	Y: 21	Y: 12	Y: 62
	K: 0	K: 23				
RGB	R: 164	R: 217	R: 217	R: 216	R: 218	R: 120
	G: 196	G: 211	G: 190	G: 202	G: 218	G: 104
	B: 32	B: 127	B: 134	B: 196	B: 218	B: 84

Power Point and Word templates were designed with two different backgrounds, light and dark (Figure 6). Moreover, to give a personal appearance to the graphic design of the presentation templates (Power Point) and other Dissemination materials, FVA have designed a graphical element retracing the logo. This element can be resized to adapt to the different Dissemination material size and proportions.

Figure 6 - Power point backgrounds

For all the presentation materials, used by all project partners (Power Point, Word, etc), the font to be used is **Trebuchet MS**.

As a general rule the text should follow the guidelines in Table 13.

Table 13 - Text colour palette

TITLES AND ALTERNATIVE BODY TEXT	BODY TEXT	TABLE STRUCTURE
Colour: Hex: #A4C421		

5.2.2 Website

The first version of SUSTRACK website was designed and deployed on M1 to give the possibility to the consortium to disseminate the project and to have an on-line presence with the relevant contents as soon as possible. The website is modular and will increase the areas and contents based on the needs of the project. The domain <https://sustrack.eu> was purchased by the Communication and Dissemination leader FVA and will be available for 10 years.

The website is aimed at the public at large and at specific stakeholders. It will also inform about SUSTRACK public activities such as workshops, presence at conferences and trade fairs, and show the project’s progress and success. Regular press-releases will be published on the website, as well as thematic factsheets on the project’s progression. The website will be promoted by all partners within their networks and institutional websites.

The main page header shows a background image with a path in the woods, representing the transition from linear to circular (Figure 7).

Figure 7 - SUSTRACK website main page header

The first version of the website has the following structure (Figure 8):

ABOUT

- **THE PROJECT** with a brief description of the project, the objectives and the methodology
- **CONSORTIUM** with the logos of the consortium partners with links to the relative websites

CASE STUDIES

Provides a short description and a list of the case studies that will be targeted by the SUSTRACK project. This area will be updated with relevant information when the project will produce content in the form of infographics, factsheets, videos etc.

NEWS

SUSTRACK-related news and events

SISTER PROJECTS

List of the SUSTRACK sister projects with a description, link to the relative website and email contact/s

JOIN AS STAKEHOLDER

Online form developed to support stakeholder recruitment. More details in Section 3.1.2.

CONTACT US

Address and google maps of the coordinator premises and email contacts of the coordinator and the Communication team

SOCIAL MEDIA

Links to Twitter and LinkedIn project Social Media channels

PRIVACY AND COOKIES POLICY

GDPR compliant privacy policy

Following are two screenshots of the SUSTRACK website.

Figure 8 - SUSTRACK website screenshots

5.2.3 Promotional material

Different promotional materials (**flyers, roll-ups, posters...**) will be designed and used for events and meetings. These materials will be available as e-files and printed on demand. SUSTRACK project will make sure to minimized the printed material in compliance with the Paperless Policy.

A **Power Point presentation about the project and its achievements** (including objectives, expected outcomes...) has been designed at M5, ready to be customized by partners depending on the purpose (Figure 9).

The presentation includes the following contents:

D6.1 Initial dissemination and communication plan

- SUSTRACK in a Nutshell (*Full name of the project, Start date and End date, Funds, Abstract, Website link and Social Media profiles*)
- Main and Specific Objectives;
- Expected outcomes/exploitable assets;
- SUSTRACK 5 Methodological steps;
- Methodologies and tools;
- Sectors of interest;
- SUSTRACK Video Teaser.

Figure 9 - Two slides of SUSTRACK Power Point presentation

A first version of the flyer, presenting the SUSTRACK project, has been designed at M6 (Figure 10).

Figure 10 - First version of SUSTRACK flyer

A first version of the roll-up, presenting the SUSTRACK project, has been designed at M5 (Figure 11).

SUSTRACK is a three year project aimed at supporting policymakers in their efforts to develop sustainable pathways to replace fossil and carbon-intensive systems with sustainable circular and bio-based systems at the EU and regional scale, contributing to achieving the European Green Deal's objectives.

PROJECT OBJECTIVES

1. To provide knowledge and tools for improving and assessing the environmental, social and economic aspects of the green, blue, circular economy and a circular bio-based economy.

2. To identify priorities and define actions to support policy makers in their efforts to promote the bio-economy transition, in combination of EU, state and cross-sectoral value chains.

SECTORS

METHODOLOGY

1. IDENTIFICATION OF THE STATUS QUO

2. DEVELOPMENT OF AN ASSESSMENT AND MONITORING FRAMEWORK

3. VALIDATION OF THE FRAMEWORK FOR THE COMPARISON OF DIFFERENT MARKET AND POLICY SCENARIOS

4. IDENTIFICATION OF POLICY PRIORITIES, ACTIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5. WIDESPREAD EXPLOITATION OF THE RESULTS

Figure 11 - First version of SUSTRACK roll-up and mock-ups

FVA will support partners with dedicated graphical material, as needed (e.g., to support events and workshops).

5.2.4 Publications and actionable knowledge

Although **publications** are not the main objective, SUSTRACK being a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) project, some partners will deliver publications. In this case, to improve the quality, efficiency and responsiveness of its research, the SUSTRACK project will make its publications available in open-access, when possible also using the [Open Research Europe Platform](#), which is an open access publishing platform for the publication of research stemming from Horizon 2020, Horizon Europe and/or Euratom funding across all subject areas. The platform makes it easy for Horizon 2020, Horizon Europe and Euratom beneficiaries to comply with the open access terms of their funding and offers researchers a publishing venue to share their results and insights rapidly and facilitate open, constructive research discussion.

Case study factsheets and videos, conference outcome factsheets, infographic cards and toolkits will be developed and produced in order to:

- inform about the development of sustainability thresholds and present a review of approaches and research gaps. Recommendations and case study assessments (including findings, recommendations and conclusions) will be reported;
- package outcomes as actionable knowledge to facilitate exploitation and adoption by stakeholders and beyond, to ensure sustainability;
- maximise the impact of the project and the awareness of the main target audiences.

In particular, **case study factsheets** will be designed, at least one per each sector, comprising one or more case studies. **Infographic cards** will provide technical information/data on general questions connected to LCA, monitoring the transition, impacts and so on. Furthermore, **7 toolkits**, in the 6 languages of the target countries and 1 in English, will be developed to make the actionable knowledge easily accessible to the stakeholders in the target countries.

5.2.5 Multimedia

A **SUSTRACK promotional video** and additional short **video teasers** will be created for the website and Social Media.

In further detail, a **Promotional video** of the project will be designed and produced in M8, with the aim of explaining in a comprehensible and attractive way the SUSTRACK objectives, target beneficiaries and expected outcomes. It will be shown by partners at their booth or on the big screen whenever they attend a symposium or trade fair, and it will be accessible from the website as well as on the SUSTRACK YouTube and Social Media channels.

The first of the two **video teasers** was already designed and produced in M1 to launch the project on the Social Media channels and embedded in the project website's main page. The strategy of the video teaser was to give at a glance a brief overview of the aim of the project (Figure 12).

Figure 12 - First video teaser screenshot

Promotional banners will be created to be deployed in the SUSTRACK Social Media channels.

Thematic cards will inform and educate various target audiences using general content, connected to the four specific sectors.

5.2.6 Dissemination and Communication materials

Based on the outcomes of the project, FVA in collaboration with the partners, will prepare at least 4 **press releases** on topics of interest to the media, in order to disseminate and communicate the results of the project to the intended audiences.

A first press release (Figure 13) has been already distributed and promoted on 8 February 2023 on the [Sustrack website](#), Social Media platforms ([Twitter](#) [LinkedIn](#)) and through partners' Press Offices. We included in the Press Release the kick-off of the project and the specific ongoing activities (see Chapter 9, Annex).

Figure 13 - First SUSTRACK Press Release

The project will inform the target audiences identified, sending at least 3 **newsletters** providing information about the main results and outcomes of the project, news, activities and events and other interesting content that will be suggested by the partners.

E-mail campaigns will be launched based on the programme of activities. The campaigns will be specifically designed to support the objectives of the activities (e.g., events) they will aim to promote.

5.2.7 Social Media

SUSTRACK project will build and animate the online presence on well-known Social Media platforms (with a focus on LinkedIn and Twitter). SUSTRACK project will use Social Media, as one of the main channels to reach primary and secondary targets, comprising Policy, Business and

financial ecosystem, Research and innovation community, Sustainability system community, Multipliers, Other EU funded projects and initiatives, as well as Civil society, Media.

The official Social Network pages of the project ([LinkedIn](#) and [Twitter](#)) have been created and launched at M1, together with the website launch.

SUSTRACK communication team (FVA) defined a consistent Social Media strategy choosing which channels and when to publish project results, news or information content, tailored to the audience across all communication channels. Moreover, all partners and their networks will be connected to the SUSTRACK Social Media profiles.

SUSTRACK communication team (FVA) intends to deploy different strategies and communication means depending on the Social Media characteristics, specifically:

The [Twitter profile](#) is a useful tool to communicate with highly educated individuals and is the channel where it is possible to reach the largest number of European projects, organizations and institutional bodies.

The [LinkedIn profile](#) is a professional Social Media site where experts share contents, network with other users, and build their personal profiles. Therefore, it is used to support connections and collaborations between the SUSTRACK project and many experts from academia, companies and B2B industries.

Finally, the [SUSTRACK YouTube channel](#) (Figure 14) was created in M1 to collect all the videos that will be produced in the context of the project activities and will contribute to a huge promotion of the project by allowing the sharing of its contents on all other social channels.

Figure 14 - SUSTRACK YouTube channel page

SUSTRACK project will continuously explore new ways of engaging more effectively with Social Media users, keeping a constant eye on broadly engaging all stakeholders, by periodically posting interesting content, experimenting with creative tools and solutions, sending out questions, and tagging relevant actors.

Specifically, the SUSTRACK project will launch **4 Social Media campaigns** in order to inform both the primary and secondary targets.

5.3 Communication support for activities organized by the partners

The SUSTRACK communication team (FVA) will support partners in their Dissemination, Communication and stakeholder engagement activities by providing:

- Graphical templates and Communication materials;
- Value propositions to communicate the activity to the intended target audience;
- Support through the Communication channels.

6 MONITORING AND REPORT

6.1 Dissemination and Communication monitoring and report

To monitor the participation of all the SUSTRACK partners in Dissemination and Communication activities and ensure that the project will reach the KPIs defined in the Grant Agreement, a monitoring report was created in the team collaboration platform to be filled by all partners. The monitoring report is composed of two tables, with dropdown menus where necessary, based on the official reporting template in the European Commission Participant Portal. The first one is to report all the Dissemination activities.

The main structure of the table is the following:

- Dissemination activity name
- Date
- Lead/Author partner
- Where? (City, Country or online)
- What? (Type of Dissemination activity)
- Number of participants
- Who? (Target audience reached)
 - Research communities
 - Industry, business partners
 - Innovators
 - Investors
 - International organisations (UN body, OECD, etc.)
 - EU Institutions
 - National authorities
 - Regional authorities
 - Local authorities
 - Civil society
 - Citizens
 - Specific end-user communities
 - Other
- Why? (Description of the objective(s) with reference to a specific project output)
- Status of the Dissemination activities
- Link to evidences

The second supports the partners in reporting Communication activities. The main structure of the table is the following:

- Communication activity name

- Date
- Lead/Author partner
- Where? (City, Country or online)
- Description
- Number of stakeholders reached
- Who? (Target audience)
- How? (Communication channel)
- Outcome (very specific KPI)
- Status
- Link to evidences

The two Tables will be periodically updated by all partners and will support the Work Package leader FVA in timely identifying critical issues that can jeopardise the impact of Dissemination and Communication. FVA will remind periodically to all partners to report on these activities.

All the activities will be reported timely in the Dissemination and Communication reporting of the EC participant portal.

An internal deep evaluation of the Dissemination, Communication (and Stakeholder engagement activities - see Section 6.2) will take place in conjunction with the first reporting period (M18). This evaluation will enable the identification and implementation of mitigation measures if some achievements and KPIs are at risk.

6.2 Stakeholder engagement monitoring and report

Monitoring stakeholder engagement is a critical aspect in SUSTRACK because the monitoring process will help to ensure that the stakeholder engagement activities are effective to reach SUSTRACK objectives and will ensure that mitigation measures are timely taken in order to fine-tune the strategy for stakeholder engagement.

To effectively monitor stakeholder engagement, the strategy envisages a framework of actionable steps to follow:

1. **Set engagement targets:** To monitor stakeholder engagement, it is important to set engagement targets and regularly track progress towards these targets. This can help identify areas where stakeholder engagement may need to be improved and provide a basis for measuring success. The engagement targets will be revised periodically, based on the project's needs.
2. **Collect feedback:** Regularly collect feedback from stakeholders to understand their perceptions and concerns related to the project. This feedback can be collected through surveys, brief meetings and interviews.
3. **Mitigation measures:** This activity will ensure timely mitigation of insufficient engagement of stakeholders in the different tasks and will set up a series of tailored interventions to ensure that the stakeholder engagement objectives are met, both quantitatively and qualitatively.
4. **Evaluate impact:** Finally, evaluate the impact of stakeholder engagement on the project's success. This can involve: the numbers of stakeholders engaged with respect to the KPIs declared (quantitative), analyzing the role that stakeholders played in shaping project

results (qualitative), and the extent to which stakeholder feedback was incorporated into project outcomes (qualitative).

Reporting stakeholder engagement will involve summarizing the key findings related to stakeholder feedback and engagement, and presenting this information in a clear and concise manner. This may include highlighting stakeholder concerns, outlining the steps taken to address these concerns, and identifying areas where stakeholder engagement could be improved. The report will also include metrics or data related to stakeholder engagement, such as the number of stakeholders engaged, the level of participation in feedback mechanisms, and the impact of stakeholder engagement on project results. Ultimately, the goal of reporting stakeholder engagement is to provide project partners with a transparent and informative summary of the project's engagement efforts and their impact on project outcomes.

7 PARTNERS' CONTACTS

Table 14 provides SUSTRACK partners' Social Media channels and online platforms.

Table 14 - Partners' Social Media channels and online platforms

PARTNERS' SOCIAL MEDIA CHANNELS AND ONLINE PLATFORMS	
Partner	Channels
UNIT	Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/Unitelma/ Instagram: http://www.instagram.com/unitelmasapienza_ig/?hl=it Twitter: https://twitter.com/UnitelmaTweet LinkedIn: http://it.linkedin.com/company/unitelma-sapienza YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCQJzmzXPQQRnr71NbYO1RVQ Website: https://www.unitelmasapienza.it/
WR	Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/WUR/ Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/uniwageningen/ Twitter: https://twitter.com/WUR LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/school/wageningenuniversity/ YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCXaytnClAXlaqlngyQh-pWg Website: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.wur.nl/en.htm • https://www.wur.nl/en/research-results.htm
KE	Twitter: @andreambassi LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/knowledge-srl/ Website: https://www.ke-srl.com/

PC	<p>Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/pedal.consulting LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/pedal-consulting/ YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/@pedalconsulting</p> <p>Website: https://pedal-consulting.eu/</p>
DBFZ	<p>Twitter: https://twitter.com/dbfz_de LinkedIn: https://de.linkedin.com/company/dbfz YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC7jmci4rJOtqNx7g_qLi8yg Flickr: https://www.flickr.com/photos/139453872@N08/</p> <p>Website: https://www.dbfz.de/</p>
UGent	<p>Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/ugent/?locale=nl_BE Instagram: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.instagram.com/woodlab.gent/ • https://www.instagram.com/ugent/?hl=en Twitter: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://twitter.com/WoodlabG • https://twitter.com/ugent LinkedIn: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.linkedin.com/company/ugent-woodlab/ • https://www.linkedin.com/school/ghent-university/ YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/user/universiteitgent</p> <p>Website: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.ugent.be/bw/environment/en/research/woodlab • https://www.ugent.be/ Newsletter: https://www.ugent.be/student/en/news-events/news</p>
TECNALIA	<p>Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/Tecnalia/ Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/tecnaliaoficial/ Twitter: https://twitter.com/tecnalia LinkedIn: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.linkedin.com/company/tecnalia-research-&-innovation/mycompany/; • https://www.linkedin.com/showcase/tecnalia-circular-economy/ YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCAuSSJiKMello2tyJpFsuKw</p> <p>Website: https://www.tecnalia.com/ Newsletter</p>
FVA	<p>Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/fvaresearch Twitter: https://twitter.com/fvawebIN LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/1899605 YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCJPSa-jueEIltyWK3jEXy_g</p>

	Website: https://www.fvaweb.eu/
Unife	<p>Facebook:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.facebook.com/profile.php?id=100057207859440; • https://www.facebook.com/sustainabilityseeds <p>Instagram:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.instagram.com/cercis_unife/?hl=en; • https://instagram.com/seeds_economics?igshid=YmMyMTA2M2Y= <p>Twitter:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://twitter.com/cercisunife?lang=en; • https://twitter.com/EconomicsSEEDS <p>LinkedIn:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.linkedin.com/company/cercis-centre-for-research-on-circular-economy-innovation-and-smes/?originalSubdomain=it; • https://www.linkedin.com/company/seeds-economics/mycompany/?viewAsMember=true <p>YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/@centreforresearchoncircula4664</p> <p>Website:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.unife.it/it; • http://www.sustainability-seeds.org/; • http://eco.unife.it/it/ricerca-impres-territorio/centri-di-ricerca/cercis?fbclid=IwAR2mzIEFNklwrlu7hqBeHEsZJgNag529KfYDzhgFvYaSOiGX1nf3_P2plg
BAM	<p>Twitter: https://twitter.com/BAMResearch</p> <p>LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/bamresearch</p> <p>YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCkkjYaE8y9NdOgl2Fy_Qiuw/featured</p> <p>Mastodon: https://social.bund.de/@BAMResearch</p> <p>Website: www.bam.de</p> <p>Newsletter: https://www.bam.de/Navigation/DE/Aktuelles/Newsletter/newsletter.html</p> <p>Mediathek: https://www.bam.de/Navigation/DE/Aktuelles/Mediathek/mediathek.html</p>
CIRCE	<p>Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/fcirce/</p> <p>Twitter: https://twitter.com/fcirce</p> <p>LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/circe-centro-tecnologico/</p> <p>YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/user/CirceResearchCentre</p> <p>Website: https://www.fcirce.es/</p>

8 CONCLUSIONS

The present deliverable is a live document and will be monitored and updated continuously, according to the natural evolution of the project and incoming opportunities during its development and promotion. FVA, as Communication and Dissemination leader, and PC, as Stakeholder engagement leader, will be proactive and motivate all partners to contribute and share content and information about the SUSTRACK project among their networks and keep track of the activities through the monitoring tools.

9 ANNEX

Design a sustainable track towards a circular bio-based economy: The SUSTRACK project will make it possible

Rome, 08/02/2023 - The [SUSTRACK project](#) gets to the core of its activities after the first preparatory phase. Funded by the European Commission as a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) and coordinated by the [UnitelmaSapienza University of Rome](#), the three-year project aims at supporting the identification of policy priorities and recommendations for designing a sustainable track towards circular bio-based systems.

"The transition from linear fossil-based systems to circular and bio-based systems represents an opportunity and a suitable pathway for achieving several Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)" says Piergiuseppe Morone, professor and researcher at [UnitelmaSapienza University of Rome](#) and SUSTRACK project coordinator. He adds *"circular bio-based systems depict a great opportunity to reconcile sustainable long-term growth with environmental protection through the cautious use of renewable resources for industrial purposes. This needed transition is a complex process, which does not simply require innovative technologies from the supply-side, but also societal transformations based on a multi-actor process."* Gülşah Yilan, the SUSTRACK project manager highlights that *"with the SUSTRACK project, we aim to support policy-makers and industries in their efforts to develop sustainable pathways to replace fossil-based, carbon-intensive systems with circular, bio-based systems."*

The circular bioeconomy meta-sector is a good candidate to push towards a new economic model, which requires transformative policies, purposeful innovation, access to finance, risk-taking capacity as well as new and sustainable business models and markets. In this context, SUSTRACK will perform a critical assessment of the impacts of the current linear fossil-based economy, as well as of the improvement potential associated with circular bio-based systems. This analysis aims to provide significant contributions to the identification of policy priorities and industrial agendas. The project builds on the extensive experiences of previous EU-funded projects such as STAR-ProBio, BIOMONITOR and STAR4BBI and involves key partners with solid expertise in circular bioeconomy impact assessment.

Currently, scientific partners are analysing the environmental, economic, and social limits of the linear, carbon-intensive and fossil-based economy while reviewing the existing information to monitor and assess the benefits of a sustainable transition to circular bio-based systems. This research also aims for defining case studies from four sectors which are facing critical challenges within the current linear economic system, namely the construction, textile, chemical and plastic sectors.

In parallel, SUSTRACK is establishing collaborations with other EU-funded projects and initiatives. In a joint effort with the European Bioeconomy Network ([EuBioNet](#)), SUSTRACK is flagged as the promoter of the working group in “Standardisation, certification, labelling and monitoring” and the main organizer of the first mobilization and mutual learning (MML) workshop. The workshop will be held on February 14th, 2023 with a dedicated focus on the engagement of eleven parallel projects to maximise the efforts and increase the networking, collaboration, knowledge sharing, mutual learning, and coordination of joint activities and events. Moreover, SUSTRACK has been invited to join the advisory board of the ongoing cluster projects SUSTCERT4BIOBASED, HARMONITOR and STAR4BBS, with the overall aim to facilitate awareness and create synergies across projects’ activities.

More information about the project, its ambitious objectives and collaboration opportunities are available on the [website](#) and the dedicated social media platforms ([Twitter](#), [LinkedIn](#)).

Project Consortium

